

EFFECT OF TWIST ON STRESS RECOVERY LENGTH FOR SINGLE YARN NATURAL FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

It is known that a single yarn is formed by spinning natural short fibers and a twist yarn consists of some single fibers in order to achieve high stiffness and strength of natural fiber composites. Generally, it is found that the amount of twist obtained by the spinning process, called twist per inch (TPI), plays an important role in yarn properties because the twist is essential to hold the fibers together. In fact, twisted yarns are normally used for increasing the lateral cohesion of the fibers and also for ease of handling. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on multiple fiber breakages and stress recovery behavior for natural fiber composites. The single yarn composites with two kinds of TPI from 1.5 and 9.5 were prepared. These yarns consisted of three single natural fibers. The fragmentation tests using these yarn composites under a polarization microscope were carried out. The multiple fiber breakages were experimentally confirmed, and it was found that the stress recovery length decreased as increase of TPI. In order to investigate the stress recovery phenomena of broken fiber, some finite element analysis were conducted. The analysis result was quantitatively agreed with experimental results. As a result, it was possible to calculate the stress recovery length of the yarn by analyzing with a model considering distance between fiber, fiber radius, resin breakage inside the yarn, etc. by finite element method analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, natural fiber composites are expected as structure material, and already applied to industrial product such as car interior parts. Natural fiber made from plants mainly consists of cellulose, which has a high elastic modulus of 138GPa in its crystal part [1]. Then it is expected that the natural fiber will widely be substituted for conventional glass fibers. A single yarn is formed by spinning short natural fibers, and a twist yarn consists of several single yarns to achieve high stiffness and strength of natural fiber composites. Generally, the amount of twist obtained by the spinning process, known as twist per inch (TPI), plays an important role in yarn properties because the twist is essential to hold the fibers together [2]. In fact, twisted yarns are normally used for increasing the lateral cohesion of filaments and for ease of handling. For glass fiber-reinforced plastic, twisted yarns are used for preparing textile preforms to increase lateral cohesion. By twisting yarns, possible micro damage within the yarn can be localized, leading to a possible increase in the yarn failure strength [3]. No significant reduction in tensile strength properties of plain weave fabric composites has been reported for E-glass yarn with a surface twist angle up to 5°. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on multiple fiber breakages and stress recovery length for single yarn natural fiber composites. The fragmentation test using single yarn natural fiber composites was carried out. Furthermore, in order to investigate the stress condition of around fiber breakage, some finite element analysis for single yarn composites were conducted.

2 MATERIALS, SPECIMENS AND IN-SITU OBSERVATIONS

2.1 Materials and specimens

The natural fiber reinforcement used in this study was a ramie single yarn (No.16, supplied by TOSCO, CO., Ltd). Some filaments were extracted from the single yarn. A yarn used in this study was manually twisted from these extracted three filaments. The numbers of twists (TPI; Twist per inch) prepared were 1.5 and 9.5 /inch. The bio-based thermosetting resin, acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESO, Ebecryl 860 produced by Daicel-allnex Co., Ltd) was used as matrix for single yarn composites. This composite is then fully bio-based composites. The hardeners for resin were a t-butyl peroxybenzoate produced by Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. The viscosity of AESO resin is 26.5 Pa s at 25 °C. The viscosity of resin decreased to add the thinner. Styrene monomer produced by Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. was used as thinner. The ratio between AESO, hardener and thinner was 100 : 1.5 : 15, at that time, the viscosity of mixed resin was approximately 2.0 Pa s. The mold jig made from a Teflon plate was shown in Figure 1-(a). The both edges of single yarn were fixed by tape, and a weight of 1.0g was applied to one edge in order to apply the constant tension for single yarn. The mold jig with single yarn having tension was sandwiched in glass plates after the resin input. The resin was cured at 100 °C for 2 hours, then a post-cured at 120 °C for 2 hours. The materials trimmed to the dimension of specimen, were buffed to mirror surface and the resin plate tabs were glued to the specimens as shown in Figure 1-(b).

(a) Mold jig to apply the constant tension

(b) Shape of the specimen

Figure 1: Specimen preparation for single yarn composites

2.2 In-situ observation system

The fragmentation tests using above yarn composites under a polarization microscope were carried out as shown in Figure 2. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature and the cross-head speed was 0.5 mm/min.

(a) Overall view

(b) Tensile loading system

Figure 2: In-situ observation system

3 FRAGMENTATION TEST RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the polarization photographs for some fiber breakages at strain level before final failure of single yarn composites. The multiple fiber breakages due to stress recovery were confirmed. In the vicinity of the fiber break, a small matrix crack occurred without fiber pull-out. From this result, it was found that the interfacial adhesion between natural fibers and AESO resin was enough. Figure 4 depicts the relation between the fiber breakage density and applied strain. The stress recovery length L_c for each TPI was estimated using equation (1),

$$L_c = \frac{4}{3} \frac{L_0}{n} \quad (1)$$

where, L_0 is the gauge length and n is the saturated number of fiber breakages. The obtained stress recovery lengths for TPI 1.5 and 9.5 were 1.67 and 1.43mm, respectively. It was found that the stress recovery length decreased as increase of TPI. From the relationship between the strain and the number of breaks, it was also confirmed that the initial fracture strain became smaller as TPI increased and the number of breaks per strain increased. From this, it can be considered that as the TPI increases, the tensile strength of the fiber decreases and the stress recovery length becomes shorter. In general, the interfacial shear strength can be calculated by Kelly-Tyson theory [4]. However, it could not be applied because it was the yarn rather than a single fiber. Therefore, finite element analysis were conducted.

Figure 3: Multiple fiber breakages using polarization observation for TPI9.5

Figure 4: Relation between the fiber breakages density and applied strain

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

4.1 FE model

In order to investigate the stress state of yarn in resin, stress analysis was performed using ANSYS ver.16.0. In the analysis, we conducted three type models in which three fibers are laid out in parallel (3FC) and models consisted of the twisted state of three fibers (TPI 1.5, 9.5). Cross-sections were observed to determine the distance between fibers and the fiber radius for the model. FE models for single yarn composites included TPI 9.5 yarn were shown in figure 5. Tetrahedral solid elements with 4 nodes and hexahedral solid elements with 8 nodes were used for matrix and fibers, respectively. These elements were assumed to be linear elastic isotropic body. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for fiber and matrix were 24.5, 0.62 GPa, 0.33 and 0.33, respectively. For the boundary conditions, on one hand the circle face was bound along the z direction and the displacement corresponding to 3.75% strain was applied on the other hands along the z direction. Moreover, to model a yarn break, cross-section of yarn near binding face was unconsolidated.

Figure 5: Finite element models

4.2 Analytical results

Figure 6 (a)-(c) show the stress contour of σ_{zz} distributions for 3FC, TPI 1.5 and 9.5 models. The obtained stress recovery behaviors were shown in figure 6 (d). It can be confirmed that the stress recovery occurred from the fiber breakage. The far field stress for each TPI was 872.2, 849.6 and 823.1MPa, respectively. It was found that the stress decreases slightly with increase of TPI. It was considered that the factor is reduction of stress due to increase twist angle.

(c) TPI 9.5 model

(d) σ_{zz} distribution diagrams

Figure 6: Stress contour of σ_{zz} for fibers

Next, the interfacial shear stress were calculated in order to investigate stress on fiber surface. Here, the stress components in the Cartesian coordinate system were transformed to the polar coordinates system at the local coordinate system which located in the center of fiber as the coordinate basis. The τ_{RZ} component was extracted at each node on the fiber surface. Figure 7(a)-(c) shows τ_{RZ} distribution for fiber surface at 0, 90, ± 180 , -90 degree in each TPI. From these results, τ_{RZ} due to broken yarn was confirmed in the vicinity of the broken yarn. It was found that the maximum value of the τ_{RZ} in TPI9.5 model. The stress recovery was due to this τ_{RZ} . Moreover, τ_{RZ} due to the load direction and the filament direction are different. It was considered that this τ_{RZ} was typical shear stress on yarn surface because it was not related to stress recovery. Consequently, it was found that the yarn surface near breakage applied two kinds shear stress.

(a) 3FC model

(b) TPI 1.5 model

(c) TPI 9.5 model

Fig.7 τ_{RZ} distribution diagrams of fiber surface

4.3 Stress recovery length estimations

Since τq represents the shear force per unit length, the sum of shear force on yarn surface along z axis $T(Z)$ was estimated by equation (2).

$$T(Z) = \sum_{i=1}^Z \sum_{j=1}^J \tau_{RZ(i,j)} \Delta q \Delta z \quad (2)$$

Where, $\tau_{RZ}(i, j)$ is the shear stress component at the node (i, j) which is located on $z=1,2,\dots,i, \dots,Z$ along z direction and on $q=1,2, \dots,j, \dots,J$ along circumference direction. The equilibrium of forces for fiber in matrix was shown in equation (3). Where, σ_f is the tensile stress, A_f is the cross-section of fiber, τ is the interfacial shear stress and q is the circumferential length of fiber.

$$\tau q \frac{L_c}{2} = \sigma_f A_f \quad (3)$$

Based on the above results, the stress recovery length was calculated using equations (2) and (3). In these equations, we proposed the stress resultant of shear stress along fiber surface area in order to consider the shear stress distribution around fiber not only along fiber direction but also along fiber perimeters. The results are shown in Table 1.

	TPI	3FC	1.5	9.5
σ_{ffar} [MPa]		872.2	849.7	825.8
$T(0.5)$ [N]		0.281	0.299	0.337
A_f [10^{-3} mm ²]		0.415	0.452	0.531
L_c [mm]		0.556	0.435	0.765
L_c (experiment)[mm]		-	1.67	1.43

Since the experimental values and analytical values are different, we investigate the reason of these differences. (1) First, the effects of fiber radius on stress distribution for TPI models were investigated. It was found that the shear stress resultant increases as fiber radius increases. (2) Then, the effects of fiber interval in yarn on stress distribution for TPI models were investigated. It was found that the stress recovery length decreases as the interval between fibers increases. It is thought that this is because τ_{RZ} inside the twisted yarn is increased as the inter-fiber distance is increase as it is not affected by each other. It was also found that the stress level decreases as the twist angle increases. (3) Next, the effect of matrix crack in yarn on the stress recovery from a fiber break was investigated. Since the results obtained from this analytical model differ from experimental values, we tried three twisted yarns as one fiber, and created a new model to break the resin inside the yarn and analyzed it. It was confirmed that σ_{ZZ} is low in the inside of the yarn around the fiber breakage. This is probably because the inner resin is broken, so that the inner side of the yarn is not responsible for the stress. From the analytical result of τ_{RZ} , it was found that τ_{RZ} contributing to stress recovery is mainly applied to the outer surface of the yarn. Furthermore, it was found that as the TPI increased, the ratio of τ_{RZ} occupied by the yarn outer portion became increase. Comparing the stress recovery length the experimental values of TPI 1.5 and 9.5 were qualitatively agreed with analytical results. (4) Finally, the elasto-plastic deformation of resin was considered in the analysis to avoid the excessive stress concentration near fiber breakage on the elastic analysis. As a result of the analysis, it was confirmed that the stress recovery became gentle as the resin part no longer bears the stress equal to or higher than the yield stress. These obtained results are shown in Table 2. The analysis result was quantitatively agreed with experimental results. As a result, it was possible to calculate the stress recovery length of the yarn by analyzing with a model considering the fiber radius, the interval between fiber, the matrix crack inside the yarn and the elasto-plastic deformation of matrix by finite element method analysis.

Table 2: Estimation for stress recovery length of elastoplastic analysis

TPI	3FC	1.5	9.5
σ_{far} [MPa]	696.5	683.2	649.65
$T(1.2)$ [N]	0.240	0.258	0.303
L_c [mm]	1.410	1.370	1.270
$L_c(\text{experiment})$ [mm]	-	1.67	1.43

5 CONCLUSIONS

The fragmentation tests using single yarn natural fiber composites under a polarization microscope were carried out in order to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on multiple yarn breakages and stress recovery length. As a result, the multiple yarn breakages due to stress recovery were confirmed and it was found that the stress recovery length decreases with increase of TPI. Moreover, in order to investigate the stress distribution and the stress recovery of broken yarn, some finite element analyses for single yarn composites under tensile loading were conducted. The z-direction stress recovery behavior was confirmed. It was considered that the stress recovery was caused by the shear stress due to broken yarn in the vicinity of the broken yarn. The shear stress on yarn due to the load direction and the filament direction are different was confirmed too. Therefore, we proposed equation for estimating the stress recovery length for yarn. It was possible to calculate the stress recovery length of the yarn by analyzing with a model considering the fiber radius, the interval between fiber, the matrix crack inside the yarn and the elasto-plastic deformation of matrix by finite element method analysis.

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